

Organ Donation- Awareness and Attitude among the General Staff Working in a Corporate Hospital in Dakshina Kannada District

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ABSTRACT

Organ donation is a life saver of patients in need. In general people are aware of organ donation, but lot of interpretation is still prevalent. Cultural practices also becomes a barrier for organ donation. With an intention of promoting organ donation among public, the present research is undertaken. By measuring the level of awareness and finding the attitude of organ donation among the general staff working in a corporate hospital in Dakshina Kannada district, the Investigator of the present study, tries to understand the appropriate strategy to promote the awareness among the people about the organ donation.

The methodology of the study includes a prospective cross-sectional research design, where all the general staff (N=150) were chosen from a corporate hospital in Mangalore. Universal sampling technique was used. The study was conducted for a period of 6 months where data was collected with the questionnaire method and information regarding awareness and attitude of the general staff in the corporate hospital was collected and analysed.

The result showed that 91.3% were aware about the organ donation. But the investigator felt that appropriate information was lacking as only 64% of them knew that both living and deceased person could donate organs, and 12% of them thought it was only the deceased person could donate and 9.3% felt it was only the living person could donate organ. So it was also seen that 77.3% felt that they required more information of organ donation. The study also showed that 14.6% of the respondents did not support the idea of organ donation, because of varied reasons like misconception of organ donation, culture, and practices of the family. The reasons for not opting for organ donation was that 2% respondents had no belief in it, 12% felt that the organ which is donated would not reach the person in need, 29.3% felt that the family members would not approve for it and 4% felt that organ donation would disfigure them. It was seen that 52.6% of them had already signed for the organ donation will. Hence the study supported that awareness is required for the public to promote organ donation.

Key words: donation, KAP, misconception, organ

INTRODUCTION

Organ donation is a noble and honourable acts which benefits many people who are in need. Organ donation could be done by a deceased person with the consent of family members, or even from a person alive. Organ donation happens in various ways, where transplantation of a healthy organ is conducted to the needy, or to self, by surgical means. It is legal process, if consensual. For organ transplantation, there should be availability of organ from a healthy donor, at the right time. Many a time, organ transplant has been failed because the patient's body is unable to accept the organ from the donor. Hence organ donation is although a delicate issue, it can be a life saver of many people. It is a delicate issue, because at times, the donors may also have little effect on their health. However, organ smuggling is also seen in the society which is the serious crime. There are also lot of mis interpretation of information by the donors and their family regarding the effect of organ donation. Hence awareness among people regarding organ donation is the burning issue of the present time. In India, the

Transplantation of Human Organs Act, 1994, controls organ donation. Any person in any manner if conducting negotiations or making arrangements or assisting with any intention, such as offering or receiving payment, or donating to a relative, or supplying human organs and tissues with any intention is subject to punishment in accordance with the applicable sections of this act. The present study makes an attempt to understand the attitude and level of awareness about organ donation among the general staff who are working in a corporate Hospital situated in Mangalore city. The data acquired will help the health care professionals to promote awareness and to increase the organ donation to help the patients who are in need. Several studies were undertaken by previous researchers, on the knowledge, attitude, and practice of organ donation. One study conducted by Sandeep Sachdeva et.al, [1] found that although people were aware about organ donation, only 26.4% consented to sign a pledge card for organ donation. This study highlighted that a high awareness but low level of positive attitude and practices were noticed among the respondents who were the visitors of a mid-level government hospital in Delhi. Another study by Kishore Y Jothula, Sreeharshika studied interns of medical college in Telegana, India. This study showed that majority of them (79.4%) had knowledge and 77.5% were willing for organ donation. But only 5.6% had donor card willingness for organ donation. The major barrier for organ donation, noticed according to this study, was fear of organ misuse[2]. Likewise, many more studies showed that although awareness was prevalent regarding the organ donation, in practice was not there. Hence the investigator of the present study, felt the need to study about the awareness and attitude about the organ donation among the general staff in the hospital to promote the organ donation.

Research methodology

The present study is descriptive, conducted with universal sampling of general staff working in a corporate hospital in Mangalore city of Dakshina Kannada district. Total of 150 coordinators working in all the departments of the hospital was considered as respondents to the study. The research was conducted for the period of 6 months, which included data collection and analysis. A pretested questionnaire was used as the tool for data collection.

Objectives of the study

The demographic profile showed that there were 57.3% females and 42.6 males. The age group of the respondents falls between 18 to 49 years, where most of them (31.3%) belonged to 34-41 years. 56% of them are graduates and only 5.33% have SSLC qualification. The environment in which the respondents work also has high chances of providing the awareness, so the duration of work of the respondents. 38.6% worked for more than 10 years and 32% of them worked for less than 3 years.

Awareness about organ donation

Result showed that 91.3% had heard about organ donation. 12% of them were aware that only deceased person can donate and 9.33% felt that the living person can only donate the organ. 19.3% of them had no information about the organ transplantation. Due to the prevalence of illegal activities with the organ donation, the Government of India has framed few laws and policies. Hence to understand the awareness regarding the law of organ donation, respondents were asked about it. 62% of them reported that they knew about the law.

The present study clearly show that awareness is promoted from the work environment. The following barchart shows that awareness can be created from the medical professional and the health care unit.

Fig. A: Source of Information

In Fig: A we can clearly see that 16% of them got information from health care unit and 15.3% from the Hospital. The remaining 15.33% got the information is through other sources like announcements from health camps, word of mouth etc.

The study also showed that 43.3% of the respondents were not aware about the place to obtain organ donation card.

Attitude about organ donation

Although 53.3% of the respondents felt that organ donation should be made mandatory after death, remaining 46.6% felt that it should not be mandatory, and family culture and practices influence this decision. Hence only 67.3% were ready to sign up as an organ donor, whereas others did not agree. 26% of the respondents reported that they would not authorise the removal of organs of their family members after death. 14.6% of them said that due to various reasons, they would not support the concept of organ donation. The respondents had their own decision in the age during which they are willing to donate the organ. The data is shown in the graph below (Fig.B)

Fig. B: Stage of life the respondents willing to donate organ

When the researcher studied their interest in donating the organs to the family members itself, majority (81.3%) showed interest.

Another area of interest in the present study was to find the opinion of the respondents, in convincing their family members to donate the organs. So the question was what would be the action plan if the family members do not agree for organ pledging. Most of them (40.6%) said that they would somehow convince the family to donate organ. 22.6% clearly opined that they would donate the organ, in spite of the objection of family. 6.6% said that they would not donate if the family objected. So here we can see the opinion varied according to the opinion of the family members.

DISCUSSION

The purpose of the present study was to understand the knowledge and attitude of general staff who are working in the health care centre about organ donation. The result of the study would be helpful to fill in the gap of knowledge of the people regarding organ donation and to promote the concept of organ donation in public. It will also be helpful in removing the misconception about organ donation. It was seen the majority of the respondents (91.3%) had heard about organ donation. Although 64% of them knew that both living and deceased person could donate organs, 12% of them thought it was only the deceased person could donate and 9.3% felt it was only the living person could donate organ. Working in hospital environment, where awareness about organ donation is sufficient, we could see that there is lack of knowledge among the respondents. This concept was also seen in a study conducted by Sandeep et.al¹, so the investigator in the present study highlights the need for promoting more awareness about organ donation in general public also. The need is felt even by the respondents because, the result showed that 77.3% felt that they required more information of organ donation. The study also showed that 14.6% of the respondents did not support the idea of organ donation, because of varied reasons like misconception of organ donation, culture, and practices of the family. The reasons for not opting for organ donation was that 2% respondents had no belief in it, 12% felt that the organ which is donated would not reach the person in need, 29.3% felt that the family members would not approve for it and 4% felt that organ donation would disfigure them.

CONCLUSION

It was seen that 52.6% of them had already signed for the organ donation will.

Analysing the result of the opinion of the respondents, the Investigator felt that awareness should be created with appropriate knowledge about the organ donation. There should be regular trainings in the hospital for the staff and also

awareness programs in the community during the health camps. The process, procedures and law should be imparted to the health care staff, so that they are well-equipped to impart knowledge to the public.

The investigator also felt the need to understand the Knowledge attitude and practice in the general public also, so future studies could be undertaken in this regard.

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REFERENCES

- [1]. Sandeep Sachdeva, Anika Sukania, Nidhi Diwedi, "Knowledge, Attitude and Practices regarding organ donation among adult visitors in public hospital in Delhi, India"; Indian j transplant 2017; 11;127-132.
- [2]. Kishore Y Jothula, Sreeharshika D, Attitude and Practice regarding organ donation among interns of a medical college in Telengana India" ; International journal of community medicine and public health;2018 Apr; 5(4);1339-1345.
- [3]. Vijayalakshmi P, Sunitha T S, Gandhi S, Thimmaiah R, Suresh Bada Math, "Knowledge, Attitude and Behavior of the general population towards organ donation: an Indian perspective"; Natl Med J India 2016; 29; 257-261.
- [4]. Rachna Gupta, Bhavana Sharma, ReenaAnand, V Som, S SKubrey, K Parati, "Knowledge Attitude & Practice regarding eye donation among people attending tertiary care hospital- a short review"; Journal of Evolution of Medical and Dental Sciences 2014; Vol. 3; Issue 02;January 13; Page: 518-525, DOI:10.14260/JEMDS/2014/1859.
- [5]. Dr.G.Bhuvaneswari, Ms.Aneesha C Anto, "A study to assess the Knowledge and Attitude regarding organ donation among staff nurses at government hospital, Thiruvallur"; International Journal of Engineering Research and General Science Volume 7; Issue 5; September-October, 2019; ISSN 2091-2730.
- [6]. Sahana B N and Sangeeta M "The Knowledge, Attitude and Practices of Medical Students regarding Organ Donation" ; Int J Cur Res Rev; Vol 7 ; Issue 16 ; August 2015; Page74-77